

PRE AND POST-OPERATIVE INTRAOCULAR PRESSURE (IOP) IN PATIENTS WHO UNDERWENT 360-DEGREE BAND BUCKLE SURGERY AT HAYATABAD MEDICAL COMPLEX, PESHAWAR

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Abstract

Background: Rhegmatogenous retinal detachment (RRD) is a vision-threatening condition that often requires surgical intervention. The 360-degree band buckle (retinal cerclage) is a modification of scleral buckling that provides circumferential support but may influence intraocular pressure (IOP). Literature remains inconsistent regarding postoperative IOP changes, with limited regional data from Pakistan.

Objective: To compare the pre- and post-operative IOP changes in patients undergoing 360-degree band buckle surgery at Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar.

Methodology: This cohort study was conducted from January to July 2025, enrolling 161 patients (161 eyes) with RRD scheduled for primary 360-degree band buckle surgery. Patients with prior glaucoma, ocular trauma, or systemic conditions affecting IOP were excluded. IOP was measured preoperatively and at one month postoperatively using Goldmann applanation tonometry. Data were analyzed using SPSS-25, with paired t-test applied to compare IOP changes. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: The mean age was 47.6 ± 9.9 years, with 94 males (58.4%). Right eye involvement occurred in 83 (51.6%) cases. The mean preoperative IOP was 12.3 ± 4.7 mmHg, which significantly increased postoperatively to 15.0 ± 3.1 mmHg (mean rise 2.7 ± 2.2 mmHg, $p = 0.045$). Elevated IOP (≥ 21 mmHg) was noted in 29 patients (18.0%), including 26 transient (16%) and 3 sustained (1.9%) cases. Hypotony (≤ 6 mmHg) developed in 4 (2.5%) patients. Stratified analysis showed no significant subgroup differences ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: 360-degree band buckle surgery results in a significant short-term rise in IOP, mostly transient and manageable. Sustained elevation and hypotony were infrequent, supporting the relative safety of this procedure. Long-term monitoring remains essential to detect late-onset pressure alterations.

INTRODUCTION

Rhegmatogenous retinal detachment (RRD) is a serious ophthalmic condition characterized by

separation of the neurosensory retina from the retinal pigment epithelium due to a full-thickness

retinal break, leading to acute vision loss and potential blindness if left untreated [1]. Globally, the annual incidence is approximately 12.17 per 100,000, with Europe showing the highest rates. This incidence is projected to double in the coming decades due to aging populations and rising myopia prevalence [2,3]. In Pakistan, RRD has been reported in 0.4% of outpatient cases, affecting predominantly young males [4]. Major risk factors include intraocular surgery, ocular trauma, and peripheral myopic degeneration. Advances in surgical approaches, such as 25-gauge pars plana vitrectomy, have achieved anatomical success rates comparable to those in developed countries [5].

Scleral buckling is a well-established treatment that closes retinal breaks and induces chorioretinal adhesion, achieving long-term success rates of about 93% in phakic eyes with uncomplicated detachments [6]. Although pars plana vitrectomy has become the preferred primary repair in many centers due to its lower recurrence rates, it carries a higher risk of cataract progression [7]. Despite a decline in popularity, scleral buckling remains valuable in younger patients and in resource-limited settings, where it offers affordability, fewer postoperative complications, and no strict postoperative positioning requirements [8].

The 360-degree band buckle, or retinal cerclage, is a modification of scleral buckling in which an encircling band supports the entire circumference of the eye. This technique seals retinal breaks, relieves vitreous traction, and promotes reattachment. It is sometimes combined with pars plana vitrectomy and has demonstrated high effectiveness in restoring retinal integrity and visual function. Newer approaches, such as the foldable capsular buckle, have further improved outcomes with shorter operative times [9,10]. Nevertheless, long-term complications, including peripheral retinal ischemia and secondary neovascular glaucoma, have been reported, emphasizing the need for careful follow-up [11].

Intraocular pressure (IOP) is a critical factor in ocular physiology, maintaining globe shape and ensuring optic nerve function. Its balance is regulated by aqueous humor dynamics through

the trabecular meshwork [12]. Disturbances in this system can lead to vision-threatening conditions such as glaucoma, where elevated IOP is a major risk factor [13]. Ocular surgeries, particularly scleral buckling, can significantly affect IOP through mechanisms including mechanical compression, altered aqueous outflow, and ciliary body dysfunction. While scleral buckling has been reported to decrease ocular rigidity and stabilize IOP fluctuations [14], procedures such as vitrectomy may elevate IOP due to the use of tamponade agents like silicone. Postoperative IOP responses vary; some patients experience short-term elevations that normalize over time, while others show persistent alterations depending on surgical technique and patient-specific factors [15,16]. Literature findings remain inconsistent, with some studies showing negligible changes and others reporting IOP elevations from buckle-induced compression [14].

Given these conflicting reports and the scarcity of regional data, particularly from Pakistan, it is important to evaluate IOP changes following 360-degree band buckle surgery. This study aims to assess pre- and post-operative IOP in patients undergoing this procedure at Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar.

METHODOLOGY

This cohort study was conducted at the Department of Ophthalmology, Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar, from January to July 2025, after approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) under reference number _____ dated _____. The sample size was calculated as 161 using OpenEpi software, based on an anticipated frequency of raise IOP after scleral buckle surgery as 28.85 [17], confidence level of 95% and 5% margin of error. Consecutive sampling was employed to recruit eligible patients. Patients of both genders, aged 18–70 years, diagnosed with RRD and planned for primary 360-degree band buckle surgery were included. Patients with a history of glaucoma, ocular hypertension, prior intraocular surgery (other than uncomplicated cataract extraction), ocular trauma, or any systemic condition affecting IOP (e.g.,

uncontrolled diabetes or steroid use) were excluded.

Baseline demographic information (age, gender, laterality of eye, systemic comorbidities) and ocular characteristics (duration of symptoms, lens status, extent of detachment, and preoperative visual acuity) were recorded using a structured proforma. IOP was measured preoperatively and postoperatively after one month using Goldmann applanation tonometry by a single experienced ophthalmologist to minimize inter-observer variability.

The surgical procedure was performed by consultant vitreoretinal surgeons using standard techniques for 360-degree encircling band buckle surgery, with or without adjunctive cryotherapy and external drainage as clinically indicated. Postoperative care included topical antibiotics and corticosteroids according to departmental protocol. The primary outcome was the change in mean IOP from baseline to postoperative follow-up visit. Secondary outcomes included the proportion of patients developing transient or sustained IOP elevation (≥ 21 mmHg) or hypotony (≤ 6 mmHg).

Data were analyzed using SPSS-25. Quantitative variables such as age, duration of symptoms, and IOP (pre- and postoperative) were presented as mean \pm standard deviation. Qualitative variables such as gender, lens status, and presence of comorbidities were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Paired sample *t*-test was used to compare pre- and postoperative IOP at different time points. Effect modifiers such as age, gender, and comorbidities were assessed through stratification. A *p*-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULT

This study included 161 eyes of 161 patients include consecutively with a mean age of 47.57 ± 9.9 years (range from 23–85 years), predominantly male 94 (58.4%). Right eye involvement was noted in 83 (51.6%) cases, while 78 (48.4%) had left eye involvement. Hypertension was present in 21 (13.0%) of patients and 16 (9.9%) were diabetics. The mean duration of symptoms was 14.50 ± 3.7 days. Regarding lens status, 115 (71.4%) eyes were phakic, 39 (24.2%) pseudophakic, and 7 (4.4%) aphakic. The extent of retinal detachment involved one quadrant in 22 (13.7%) patients, two quadrants in 44 (27.3%), three quadrants in 63 (39.1%), and total detachment in 32 (19.9%). Preoperative visual acuity was $\geq 6/18$ in 21 (13.0%), between $<6/18$ – $6/60$ in 74 (46.0%), and $<6/60$ in 66 (41.0%). The mean preoperative intraocular pressure (IOP) was 12.3 ± 4.7 mmHg. The figure -1 demonstrate that the majority of patients, 108 (67.1%), underwent 360° band buckle surgery alone. Adjunctive cryotherapy was performed in 96 (59.6%) cases, while external drainage was required in 41 (25.5%) patients. A smaller proportion, 12 (7.5%), underwent combined 360° band buckle with vitrectomy.

At one month, the mean postoperative IOP increased significantly from baseline by 2.7 ± 2.2 mmHg (*p* = 0.045), reaching 15.0 ± 3.1 mmHg. Elevated IOP occurred in 12 patients (7.4%), including 9 (5.6%) transient and 3 (1.86%) sustained cases, while 4 patients (2.5%) developed hypotony (table-1).

Stratified analysis showed a postoperative IOP rise across all subgroups, with slightly higher mean increases in patients ≤ 40 years (2.55 ± 2.17 mmHg) and phakic eyes (2.43 ± 2.18 mmHg). However, none of the differences reached statistical significance (*p* > 0.05) (table -2).

Figure 1: Surgical details of patients undergoing 360° band buckle

Table 1: Postoperative Intraocular Pressure Outcomes (at 1 Month, n = 161)

Variable	Mean ± SD / Frequency (%)
Postoperative IOP (mmHg)	15.0 ± 3.1
Mean change in IOP (post - pre)	2.7 ± 2.2
p-value (paired t-test)	0.045
IOP elevation (≥21 mmHg)	29 (18.01%)
Transient (resolved within 1 month)	26 (16.14%)
Sustained (>1 month)	3 (1.86%)
Hypotony (≤6 mmHg)	4 (2.5%)

Table 2: Stratified Analysis of Pre vs Post-op Mean IOP Change

Variable	Mean IOP Change (mmHg)	p-value
Age ≤40 years	2.55 ± 2.17	0.09
Age >40 years	2.27 ± 2.33	0.22
Male	2.32 ± 2.21	0.13
Female	2.10 ± 2.15	0.28
Phakic	2.43 ± 2.18	0.12
Pseudophakic	2.20 ± 2.30	0.10

DISCUSSION

Our study compare the pre- and post-operative IOP outcomes in patients undergoing 360-degree

band buckle surgery for RRD at a tertiary care center in Peshawar. The mean age of patients was 47.6 years, with the majority falling between 40-50 years, and males predominating (58.4%). These

findings are consistent with the study of Moorfields Buckle that documented a median follow-up age of 40.39 years, reflecting that RRD commonly affects middle-aged adults [18]. In contrast, Kazaikin et al. (2024) noted a slight female predominance (56%) across a broader age range, highlighting geographic and population-specific variability [19]. The predominance of male gender in our study aligns with prior local observations that RRD in Pakistan tends to affect relatively younger males [4].

In our study, most patients (71.4%) were phakic, 24.2% were pseudophakic, and 4.4% were aphakic. This distribution is in agreement with the literature that the majority of scleral buckling cases were phakic eyes, supporting the notion that lens status does not significantly influence the decision for scleral buckling [20]. A study further observed that intraocular lens type did not significantly affect outcomes in pseudophakic eyes, although monofocal lenses showed slightly better anatomical results [21].

Regarding disease extent, our patients presented with varying severity: 39.1% had three-quadrant involvement, and 19.9% had total retinal detachment. Since macula-off detachments are associated with worse visual prognosis [20], early detection and timely intervention remain crucial in improving outcomes.

Most patients (67.1%) in our study underwent 360° band buckle alone, with adjunctive cryotherapy in 59.6% and external drainage in 25.5%. Only 7.5% required combined buckle and vitrectomy. Literature suggests that scleral buckling remains a viable alternative to pars plana vitrectomy (PPV), with reported primary attachment rates as high as 93% [20]. Personalized buckle approaches and optimized drainage techniques have been proposed to further reduce complications [19,22]. Our adjunctive use of cryotherapy is in line with previous findings that cryotherapy before drainage is safe and does not increase complications [23].

The mean preoperative IOP in our patients was 12.3 mmHg, which increased significantly by 2.7 mmHg postoperatively ($p = 0.045$), reaching 15.0 mmHg at one month. Elevated IOP (≥ 21 mmHg) was noted in 18.01% of cases, mostly transient.

This incidence is considerably lower than the 28.85% postoperative IOP rise reported in literature [17], possibly due to differences in patient demographics, surgical techniques, or follow-up duration. In comparison, a study conducted by Almeida et al. (2013) reported ocular hypertension in 20.2% of vitrectomy patients, suggesting that scleral buckling may pose a relatively lower risk of pressure elevation compared to PPV [24].

Our study also observed hypotony in 2.5% of cases, which is clinically relevant though less frequently discussed in literature. Long-term studies, have shown that encircling scleral buckles may predispose patients to chronic pressure alterations, with 13% developing perimetric glaucoma [25]. Hence, while our short-term results are reassuring, extended monitoring is warranted.

Limitations and Future Recommendation

Limitations of our study include the short follow-up period of one month, which restricts assessment of long-term IOP fluctuations and glaucoma risk. Additionally, as a single-center study, the findings may not be generalizable to broader populations. Long follow-up study including multi-center is recommended for reliable results.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated a statistically significant rise in mean intraocular pressure following 360-degree band buckle surgery for rhegmatogenous retinal detachment, with most cases showing transient and clinically manageable changes. The incidence of sustained IOP elevation and hypotony was low, underscoring the relative safety of this procedure. Given the known risk of long-term pressure alterations and secondary glaucoma after encircling buckles, careful postoperative surveillance remains essential. While our findings highlight the continued value of scleral buckling in resource-limited settings, further multicenter studies with longer follow-up are needed to better define long-term IOP outcomes and optimize management strategies.

Conflict of Interest: Nothing to declare

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Data Availability Statement: Will be provided on request

Contribution:

- **XXXX:** Manuscript writing, data collection, and responsible for the integrity of the study.
- **XXXX:** Concept of the study

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